

THE INFLUENCE OF DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS ON EMPLOYEE STRESS: A STUDY IN COMILLA BSCIC, BANGLADESH

Shaikh Moksadur Rahman

Associate Professor

Department of Management Studies
Comilla University, Comilla-3506
Bangladesh

Abstract:

Job stress is considered an important workplace health risks and mental disorder for employees both in developed and developing countries. It worsens interpersonal relationships at work, such as conflicts with the behavior of supervisors, conflicts with colleagues, conflicts with subordinates and conflicts with management policies which ultimately affect productivity. Level of stress also affects job satisfaction, absenteeism, accident and turnover. On realizing the importance of this issue, the present study was conducted to assess the existing state of some selective demographic factors which critically influence the employee stress. A sample of 167 employees from the Industry Sector from Comilla BSCIC, Bangladesh was used for this analysis. The present states of employee stress on various demographic factors were measured through mean scores with the help of a five-point Likert Scale. The critical factors that affect the employee stress were identified and their contribution to the existing state of stress was measured by inter-correlation matrix and multiple regression technique. The study finds that the most important factors contributing to the level of stress of employee were inadequate salary followed by the factors, working tenure and position. If the findings of this study are rightly perceived and do act in accordance by the policy maker and industrialist, it may be said that harmonious industrial relations will prevail in manufacturing sectors in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Demographic factors, employee stress, BSCIC, Bangladesh

INTRODUCTION:

Stress has been defined as the interaction between the individual and the environment characterized by physiological and psychological changes that cause a deviation from normal performance. This deviation from normal may have a positive or negative outcome. A moderate amount of stress can help to stimulate employees to work longer, harder, and better. However, an extremely low level of stress can leave employees unstipulated, resulting in low productivity. An extremely high level of stress can lead to poor performance due to the diversion of increased energy from production and to dealing with the stress itself (Locke, 1983; Anthony et al. 2001, Rahman, 2012). Other consequences of stress include various dysfunctional behaviors that detract from, rather than contribute to, organizational performance. The medical consequences of stress affect a person's physical well-being. Heart disease and stroke, among other illnesses, have been found to be linked to stress. Other common medical problems resulting

from too much stress include headaches, backaches, ulcers and related stomach and intestinal disorders, and skin conditions like acne and hives (Anthony et al. 2001, DeNishi and Griffin, 2009).

Stress has both an internal and external factor. Internal factors are primarily a person's attitudes and expectations. Internal factor includes demographic variable such as age, sex, religion, position etc. It is difficult to categorize the factors as high level or low level or to even list them because a situation that creates a high level of stress for one person may not cause any stress for another. Further, a person who views a situation as stressful one day may not view it as stressful on another day (Anthony et al. 2001, DeNishi and Griffin, 2009; Rahman, 2012).

Several studies have tried to identify the relationship between demographic factors and job stress. In recent years demographic factors and job stress are the two important issues in human resource management researches. According to DeNishi (2009) demographic factors have been found having significant relationship with job stress. One study of employees working in call centers in US identified different stressors; one of which was demographic factor that was predictive of job dissatisfaction (Tuten and Neidermeyer, 2004). It appears that stress first manifests itself as an increase in job dissatisfaction, which may lead to an increase in quitting intent (or an increase in absenteeism). The relationship between stress at work and non work conflict has been documented largely in manufacturing industries and within service industries. Logically, there is a link between investments of time and emotional involvement in employment and the degree to which those investments invade (or even represent withdrawals in) one's home life (Van et al. 1981; Tuten and Neidermeyer, 2004). Thus it is proved that one's home life is influenced by demographic variables.

The study conducted by Messei, et al., 2002; Van et al., 1981; Tuten and Neidermeyer, 2004 found that some demographic factors such as age, sex, experience and level of education of employees influence the level of stress. They explained that both positive and negative phenomenon of the factors, age and sex had negative influence but experience and level of education had positive influence i.e. when experience of employee was higher, level of stress were higher and as the same result was reported for level of education. The studies of Dyer and Quine, 1998; DeNishi, and Griffin, 2009, found positive relationship between age and stress, no relationship between sex and stress. They also found the positive relationship between service tenure and stress but they found no relationship between level of income and stress. One study titled 'The Relationship among Job Stress and Job Satisfaction in Municipality Personnel in Iran' conducted by Bemana et al. (2013) found that there was no significant differences between two genders in job stress.

As human being's perception, feeling, emotion, taste etc are different from others and as they are changing, the nature of relation between demographic factors and stress is complex. As a result, the different literatures show different results. For example, some scholars show in their study, male employees are more stressful than women, on the other hand, some scholars find no significant differences between men's and women's stress level. Some researchers found in their study, aged persons were more stressful than younger. Some researchers showed

completely different result i.e. younger persons are more stressful than aged person. Some showed negative relationship between level of income and stress and some researchers depicted no relationship between stress and level of income. But most of the researchers (Van et al., 1981; Locke, 1983; Martin and Miller, 1986; Dyer and Quine 1998; Tuten and Neidermeyer, 2004; Rahman, 2012; Poorna and Anandaraj, 2013) acknowledge that long lasting stress caused by organization leads to extreme job dissatisfaction by which the employee feel the organization growth is worthless in the context of his/her own interest, employees try to run away from the organization and they do not try to the development of the organization.

Literature Review:

Employee stress has been studied intensively in the developed countries especially in western nations, but only a few studies have been conducted in under-developed and developing countries. Indeed, stress has been a matter of growing interest for those concerned with the quality of working life and industrial efficiency based on demographic variables. The consequences of employee stress are very important to an organization in terms of its efficiency, productivity, employee relations, mutual understanding among management and peer colleagues, trust, mental peace, health hazard, absenteeism, accident and turnover.

The development of interest in stress in organization settings is not a recent phenomenon. In fact, Kahn et al., 1964; Krejcie and Morgan, 1970; Fletcher & Payne 1971; House and Rizzo, 1972; Hall & Gordon 1973; Caplan et al., 1975; Beehr and Newman, 1978; Van et al., 1981; Locke, 1983; Stamps & Piedmonte, 1986; and Martin & Miller, 1986 monograph entitled Job Stress originated what has become a major area for managers and workers alike in many different settings. It is also one of the most widely discussed issues in the field of industrial and organizational psychology.

Previous research on stress among employees, particularly in the service sectors and somewhat in the manufacturing industries during the last decade, has focused primarily on the possibility of adapting a resolution of relationship between employee stress and job satisfaction in the form of anxiety and low job satisfaction. However, job related demographic factors such as age, sex, working tenure, education etc. that affect stress could all be considered as creating conditions which impair individuals in their efforts to do their work effectively (Van et al., 1981; Locke, 1983; DeNishi and Griffin, 2009). Nevertheless, the complexity of job stress and the problem of group dynamics are among the most germane issues facing modern management. Their most unpleasant manifestation appears in statistics of absenteeism, accident, turnover and decreasing productivity. Excessive changes in absenteeism, burnout, dispute, accident, turnover and low productivity result in a social waste of manpower and unnecessary loss in production and profit (Van et al., 1981; Locke, 1983; Martin and Miller, 1986; DeNishi and Griffin, 2009).

Relevance of the Study:

A sound system of industrial relations and the maintenance of industrial peace is an important pre-requisite for any developing economy. The harmonious relationship between the management and the workers has a vital role in the

establishment of industrial discipline, industrial democracy and industrial peace and it has a far reaching impact on productivity, labor efficiency and social welfare (Locke, 1983; Anthony et al. 2001, Jesily, 2013; Poorna and Anandaraj, 2013).

Industrial relations denote a highly complex and dynamic process of relationship involving the workers and the management as well as their collective forums and the state. The absence of industrial dispute does not mean that the complete harmony prevails in the labor-management relations (Anthony et al. 2001; DeNishi and Griffin, 2009; Jesily, 2013). The discontent between the management and the labor is due to some job-related factors and demographic factors. The labor productivity and unit labor cost for Bangladesh in comparison with advanced and developing countries are much lower. The causes of lower productivity are conventional technology, inadequate infrastructural facility and poor management. The labor cost per hour in USA is 25 dollar where it is only 12 cents in Bangladesh (Saiyed, 2014). The Labor cost is constituted only a small portion of total cost of production in developing countries like Bangladesh. Tasin (2013) mentioned in her article published in The Daily Star, Bangladesh - Cheapest labor is abundant in Bangladesh, some of workers are willing to work at a wage rate of \$0.20 an hour. This is less than a fifth of the labor costs in China. The unit labor costs are about half of that of Cambodia and India (ADB, 2014). This situation may be stated as a reason of lack of job facility, inadequate bargaining capacity and lack of government policy. Deplorable socio-economic conditions enhance the level of stress of the industrial employees in developing countries causing violence and disruption of industrial growth (DeNishi and Griffin, 2009; Jesily, 2013; Poorna and Anandaraj, 2013). Work place violence and aggression are also growing concerns in many organizations. People who are having problems with stress may vent their difficulties by yelling at or harassing their colleagues. They may also engage in other destructive behaviors such as damaging company property or physically assaulting their boss or a co-worker (DeNishi and Griffin, 2009). Violence by disgruntled workers or former workers results in many deaths and injuries each year in Bangladesh.

Bangladesh is mainly an agrarian country having 153.60 million people and its population growth rate was 1.5% during 2008 – 2013. In 2010, the population living below the national poverty line was 31.3% (ADB, 2014). After its liberation since 1971, industrial sector is being considered as one of the growing sectors of economy by creating huge employment opportunities, income generation and sustainable development. This sector comprises different operations such as mining and quarrying, manufacturing, power, gas and water supply, construction etc. The contribution of industry to GDP in 2014 was 27.71%. Manufacturing industries comprise large & medium scale and small scale; their contributions were 13.7% and 5.2%, respectively (BB, 2014). But since last ten years, this sector is facing immense problems like labor unrest due to poor industrial relations hindering its growth. Not only foreign investors but also domestic investors are reluctant to invest in manufacturing sector due to frequent labor unrest (CPD, 2013). So there is a need to find the impact of demographic variables on job stress in manufacturing sector of Bangladesh. The researcher hopes that finding of this study will add value as sample research from a developing world country like Bangladesh.

On realizing the importance of this issue, the present study was made to assess the existing state of employee stress, to analyze the demographic factors and to identify the critical ones among them that affect stress. As mentioned earlier the stress of employee is influenced by both internal and external factors. The external factors include economic, social and political affairs, which emanate from outside the purview of the industry over which the management may have little or no control. There are many factors emanating from and within the employees and organization such as age, sex, working tenure, education, position and monthly salary, job interest, working conditions, welfare measures etc., which are referred to as an internal factors. Many research studies have indicated that the internal factors have potential influence on employee stress (Jesily, 2013; Poorna and Anandaraj, 2013). If any one of the internal factors is likely to cause employee stress to a considerable extent, the constraint should be removed and the working conditions, employee mix etc. need to be changed. The studies, conducted on stress in India, Pakistan, Iran and many other Asian countries concerning with job satisfaction, considered work related factors such as working condition, job security, welfare measures, supervision etc., but little importance were given on demographic variables. The present study wants to measure the level of stress on the basis of some selective demographic variables.

Objectives:

Having favorable investment climate in Bangladesh, the number of industry increased during last few years but the industrial contribution to GDP is still very low. At present the overall economic growth is 6.06% If Bangladesh wants to become a middle income country by 2021, the overall growth should be more than 8%. This growth can be attained by flourishing all the arenas of economy, especially industrial sector. In recent years, industrial growth in Bangladesh halted by industrial dispute due to stress caused by different demographic causes are considered as great threats of development. The employees with a higher level of occupational stress may not be satisfied with their job and therefore they will not feel happy working in the organization. They may feel frustrated or burned out when they are having problems with colleagues and employers. It may produce a negative impact to the organization itself. Therefore, it is very important for employer to realize the stress and the stressor that cause all the negative effects. The following are the main objectives of the study:

1. To measure the level of stress on the basis of some selective demographic factors;
2. To find out the critical factors which lead to high stress;
3. To offer suitable suggestions for policy makers and industrialists to overcome stress.

Material and Methods:

Area profile: Bangladesh Small and Cottage Industries Corporation (BSCIC) is the prime mover organization entrusted with the responsibility of development of small and cottage industries (SCI) in Bangladesh. It is an autonomous corporation under the Ministry of Industries and was established by an Act of the parliament in 1957. It is the successor organization of EPSCIC. Bangladesh Small & Cottage Industries Corporation (BSCIC) was established in recognition of the need for a specialized agency to promote the development of Small, Medium &

Rahman . S.M / The Influence of Demographic Factors on Employee Stress: A Study in Comilla Bscic, Bangladesh

Cottage Industries (SMCIs) in the manufacturing sector through the provision of advisory services, fiscal and financial assistance, infrastructural facilities, market access and other support programs. BSCIC strives to create resilient and efficient SMCIs, able to compete in a liberalized market environment. SMCIs have to be efficient and knowledge-driven, including using ICT to be globally connected and accessible. Bangladesh Small & Cottage Industries Corporation is expected to promote SMCIs that to be an integral part of the country's industrial development capable of producing high value-added manufacturing product and services. The principal goal of the Bangladesh Government economic policy is to reduce poverty which is coherent with the Millennium Development Goals by rapid industrialization (BSCIC, 2014). BSCIC has developed a total of 74 industrial estates throughout the country to foster the growth of Small and Cottage Industries in a balanced manner.

BSCIC, Comilla was established in 1961 with an aim to accelerate pace of growth and development of the local small and cottage industries comprising different types of industries such as food product, jute, leather, metal product, plastic product, rice mills, wheat mills, sea foods, textiles etc. There are 133 operational units engaged in different types of consumer and industrial goods. The main objective of BSCIC, Comilla is to support the development of local industrial entrepreneur. It has a major contribution in absorbing majority unemployment by employing a good number of local people. It is the second largest sector after Comilla EPZ, in employing majority unemployed people (BSCIC, 2014).

Sample: This study was conducted in March – April, 2014 in Comilla BSCIC, Bangladesh. Using the simple random sampling technique, a total of 210 respondents were selected as a sample of the study from that industrial estate. The respondents come from various employees engaged in different production activities in order to get better mixture among respondents to increase the generalization of the result. The valid respondent was 167 (response rate was 79.52%) which was very much acceptable in social science research. Table 1 shows the respondent's profile.

Measurements: In the study, demographic variables such as age, sex, working tenure, education, position and salary are considered as independent variables which affect dependent variable such as stress. Variable measurements employed in this study are well defined and developed tools from previous studies. Job stress is measured by “Job Stress Questionnaire, ‘JSQ’ proposed by Caplan et al. (1975) and Stress Management at Work by AIPM (2014) with somewhat modified form on the basis of practical situation composed with thirteen dimensions, namely; ‘disagreement and indecision’, ‘pressure on the job’, ‘job description conflict’, ‘communication and comfort with supervisor’, ‘job related health concerns’, ‘work overload stress’, ‘work under load stress’, ‘boredom induced stress’, ‘problem of job security’, ‘time pressure’, ‘job barrier stress’, ‘salary & promotion’ and ‘physical’. Each of job stressors was measured on a five-point Likert Scale in which [1] indicated “never”, [2] indicated “rarely”, [3] indicated “occasionally”, [4] indicated “usually” and [5] indicated “constantly”. There are five facets in each thirteen dimensions. For example, under the dimension of ‘disagreement and indecision’, five facets are: (i) Unsure of

coworkers' expectations; (ii) Unfriendly attitude in coworkers; (iii) Job responsibilities go against your better judgment; (iv) Can't satisfy conflicting demands from superiors; (v) Trouble refusing overtime.

Reliability: The internal reliability of the items used was verified by adapting the Cronbach's alpha (George and Mallery, 2003). George and Mallery provide the following rules of thumb: >.9 – 'Excellent', >.8 – 'Good', >.7 – 'Acceptable', >.6 – 'Questionable', >.5 – 'Poor', and <.5 – 'Unacceptable' (p. 231). The Cronbach alpha estimated for Disagreement and Indecision was 0.821, Pressure on the Job was 0.940, Job Description Conflict was 0.767, Communication and Comfort with Supervisor was 0.795, Job Related Health Concerns was 0.806, Work Overload Stress was 0.755, Work Under Load Stress was 0.762, Boredom Induced Stress was 0.872, Problem of Job Security was 0.934, Time Pressure was 0.756, Job Barrier Stress was 0.726, Salary & Promotion was 0.805 and Physical was 0.871. As the Cronbach's alpha in this study were all much higher than 0.6, the constructs were therefore deemed to have adequate reliability.

Tools of analysis: Respondent's profile was reported in percentages value. Job stress containing thirteen dimensions were presented by descriptive statistics. For the purpose of in-depth analysis, statistical tools, inter-correlation matrix and multiple regression technique had been used. The data analysis was done by using SPSS 16 version.

Table 1: Respondent Profiles (independent variables)

Characteristic	Number	Percentage	Characteristic	Number	Percentage
Age (year):			Education:		
< 25	94	(56.29%)	Illiterate	16	(9.58%)
25 – 30	33	(19.76%)	Primary	70	(41.92%)
30 – 35	18	(10.78%)	High School	67	(40.12%)
35 – 40	16	(9.58%)	College	8	(4.79%)
> 40	6	(3.59%)	University	6	(3.59%)
Sex:			Position:		
Male	130	(77.84%)	Worker	101	(60.48%)
Female	37	(22.16%)	Supervisor	49	(29.34%)
Working tenure (year):			Pro Manager	17	(10.18%)
< 2	16	(9.58%)	Monthly Salary (Tk.):		
2 – 5	86	(51.50%)	< 3000	24	(14.37%)
6 – 9	29	(17.37%)	3000 – 6000	69	(41.32%)
10 – 13	25	(14.97%)	6000 – 9000	27	(16.17%)
> 14	11	(6.59%)	9000 - 12000	18	(10.78%)
			12000 - 15000	20	(11.98%)
			> 15000	9	(5.39%)

Result and Discussion:

Table 2 shows the minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation and rank of dependent variables. The total score of stress of all 167 workers were summed up separately for each facet. It is clear from the table that the facets were not rated equally by the employees. The 'job description conflict' with a mean value 2.0383 depicted no stress stood first position in ranking But 'Salary and promotion' with a mean value 4.1838 depicted stresses stood thirteenth position followed by 'problem of job security' (3.7042).

Table 2: Minimum, Maximum, Mean, Standard Deviation and Rank of Dependent Variables

Dependent variables	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev	Rank
Disagreement and Indecision	1.60	5.00	2.9123	0.7963	8
Pressure on the job	1.60	5.00	2.4172	0.7191	3
Job description conflict	1.60	5.00	2.0383	0.7537	1
Communication and comfort with supervisor	1.80	4.60	2.8731	0.6634	7
Job related health concerns	1.60	5.00	3.2263	0.8418	9
Work overload stress	1.60	5.00	2.5772	0.7328	4
Work under load stress	1.60	4.80	2.5997	0.7309	5
Boredom induced stress	1.20	4.40	3.3647	0.7178	10
Problem of job security	2.00	4.80	3.7042	0.9151	12
Time pressure	1.20	4.60	3.4616	0.6655	11
Job barrier stress	1.60	5.00	2.1240	0.7217	2
Salary and promotion	2.00	5.00	4.1838	0.7377	13
Physical	2.00	5.00	2.7305	0.6694	6
Overall stress	2.72	3.85	3.3030	0.2345	

In this analysis, an attempt is made to assess the relative importance of the demographic variables and also to identify the most critical among them. The total seven variables (one dependent and six independent) selected for the study were correlated with one another through inter-correlation matrix, the results are presented in the Table 3. The first column of inter-correlation matrix shows that except ‘sex’, all other five factors were significantly correlated to stress. However, the under mentioned inter-correlation matrix cannot clearly state whether the correlations shown in the different column were genuine or false, as these were only zero-order correlations and also because there may be a multi colinearity among the six variables. As already mentioned, one of the objectives of this study was to identify the combination of demographic variables, which together were most critical in explaining variations in stress. Therefore, these correlations were subjected to multi-variant analysis using multiple regression technique.

Table 3: Inter-correlation Matrix for Employee Stress and Demographic Factors (Zero-order)

Variables	Y	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6
Employee stress	1						
Age	0.376**	1					
Sex	0.006	-0.117	1				
Working tenure	0.373**	0.883**	0.066	1			
Education	0.317**	0.257*	-0.049	0.103	1		
Position	-0.373**	-0.610**	-0.077	0.736**	-0.346**	1	
Salary	-0.455**	0.881**	0.000	0.977**	0.307**	0.762**	1

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2- tailed)

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2- tailed)

It was decided that for a combination of the factors to be accepted, it must satisfy the following additional requirements.

(1) It should explain maximum variation in stress, as measured through adjusted coefficient of demographic variables (R^2). (2) The net combination of each variable should be positive/negative and (3) The net contribution of each and every variable should be statistically significant.

Table 4: ANOVA^b Table for Testing Multiple Regression

Source	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	F	Significance
Regression	1.955	6	0.326	7.262	.000 ^a
Residual	7.180	160	0.045		
Total	9.135	166			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Age, Sex, Experience, Education, Position, Salary

b. Dependent Variable: Stress

The Table 4 presented ANOVA was prepared to test the overall statistical significance of the factors. The table shows that the regression as a whole was significant. Therefore, it was statistically possible to proceed with the multiple regression analysis. The multiple regression technique was carried out by keeping the criteria in the background. The regression results are presented in the Table 5. The multiple regression analysis depicts that there were three variables namely ‘working tenure’, ‘position’, and ‘salary’ which meet all the conditions in the selection of the criteria. Out of three variables, ‘salary’ contributed more toward employee stress, i.e. every one unit change in ‘salary’, by keeping all other independent variables constant, it would result in 0.3460 unit change in the employee stress. It was followed by ‘working tenure’ and ‘position’ and they contributed to the extent of 0.1853 and 0.1624 unit change respectively in stress for every one unit change in them. The independent variables accounted for 63 percent of the variations in the total variations of the dependent variable. The Table 5 depicts that ‘age’, ‘sex’ and ‘education’ had no significance influence on employee stress.

Table 5: Multiple Regression Analysis for Demographic Factors

Independent Variable	Co-efficient (Beta)	t- statistics
Age	0.0612	1.0145
Sex	0.0207	0.4994
Working tenure	0.1853**	3.0370
Education	0.1009	1.6581
Position	0.1624*	2.8842
Salary	- 0.3460**	- 5.1543

* $P \leq 0.05$, ** $P \leq 0.01$, $R^2 = 0.6330$

Findings and conclusion:

The study has indicated that although all the three variables were statistically significant to the employee stress, ‘salary’ was the most important demographic factor among the three affected negatively, it was followed by the factors ‘working tenure’ and ‘position’ affected the stress positively. Therefore, it is clear that unless the basis

Rahman . S.M / The Influence of Demographic Factors on Employee Stress: A Study in Comilla Bscic, Bangladesh

economic needs of the employee of the manufacturing industry were met regularly and adequately, any attempt for improving the situation by changing the employee mix may not result in stress. The monetary factor is one of the most important factors which has strong influence on keeping harmonious industrial relations. If the findings of this study are rightly perceived and do act in accordance by the policy maker and industrialist, it may be said that harmonious industrial relations will prevail in manufacturing sectors in Bangladesh.

Limitations and scope for further study:

The researcher wanted to conduct a study on both Comilla EPZ and Comilla BSCIC but due to not having permission from EPZ authority the study was confined in only Comilla BSCIC. BSCIC has developed a total of 74 industrial estates throughout the country to foster the growth of Small and Cottage Industries in a balanced manner. The limitations of this study are: firstly, data has been collected through questionnaire from only one industrial estate comprising different operational units. Second, the study assumed only demographic factors, age, sex, working tenure, education, position and salary as predictors of employee stress, though many other factors such as job security, job interest, labor-management relations, supervision, working environment are perpetually accounts for stress. Caution should be made that findings of this preliminary study should not be generalized to the larger population due to its small sample size. A wide range sample would be needed to represent the general population. Further intensive research is necessary to explore deeper into the causes of stress and its effect on employees job satisfaction.

Reference:

American Institute for Preventive Medicine (AIPM), Stress Management at Work <http://www.healthylife.com/online/stress/StateOfMichigan/work-stessor-questionnaire.html>, Accessed: 5th February, 2014.

Anthony, W. P., Perrew, P. L., Kaomar, K. M. (2001). Human Resource Management, A Strategic Approach, Third Edition, The Dryden Press, USA, pp. 541 – 549.

Asian Development Bank (ADB, 2014). Bangladesh Quarterly Economic Update, Bangladesh Resident Mission, Dhaka, Bangladesh. pp. 8 – 11.

Bangladesh Bank (BB), Annual Report, 2012 – 13 (2014), Bangladesh: Some Selected Statistics, Appendix-3, Table-V: Growth and Sectoral Share of GDP (at FY96 constant prices), p. 231.

Bemana, S., Moradi, H., Ghasemi, M., Mehdi, S., Taghavi and Ghayoor, A. H. (2013). The Relationship among Job Stress and Job Satisfaction in Municipality Personnel in Iran, World Applied Sciences Journal 22 (2): 233-238.

Beehr, T. A. and Newman, J. E. (1978). Job stress Employee Health and Organizational Effectiveness: A facet Analysis, model and literature review, Personnel Psychology, p. 31

Centre for Policy Dialogue (CPD, 2013), Bangladesh Economy in FY 2014, Three Months after the Budget, Three months before the Elections, Dhaka, Bangladesh, pp. 4 – 22.

Caplan, R. D., Cobb, S., French, J. R. P, Harrison, J. R. V. and Pinneau, S.R. P. (1975) Job demands and Worker Health, HEW Publication No. (NIOSH), pp: 75-160.

DeNishi, A. S. and Griffin, R. W. (2009). Human Resource Management, Houghton Mifflin Co., USA. pp. 492 – 499.

Dyer, S., & Quine, L. (1998). The effects of job demands and control on employee attendance and satisfaction, *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, 12, pp.596-608.

Fletcher, J. B. and Payne, R. (1971). Stress and Work: A Review and a Theoretical Framework, Part 1, *Personnel Review*, 9, pp. 1-20.

George, D. and Mallery, P. (2003). *SPSS for Windows step by step: A simple guide and reference*. 11.0 update (4th ed.). Boston: Allyn & Bacon. P.231.

House, R. J. and Rizzo, J. R. (1972). Role conflict and ambiguity as critical variables in a model of organizational behavior, *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, Vol. 7, pp. 467- 505.

Jesily, M. (2013). Job-Related Factors Vis-à-vis Labor-Management Relations, Prabandhan: *Indian Journal of Management*, Issue: March, pp. 27 – 33.

Krejcie, R. V. and Morgan, D. V. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30, pp. 607-610.

Locke, E. (1983). The nature and causes of job satisfaction. In M.D. Dunnette ((Ed.) *Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, pp: 1297-1349. New York, NY: John Wiley and sons,Inc.

Martin, J. K., and Miller, G. A. (1986). Job Satisfaction and Absenteeism: Organizational, Individual and Job-related Correlates. *Work and Occupations*, 13(1), pp. 33-46.

Messei, G. L., Ronen, H. and Taylor, A. (2002), Organizational stress as the barrier to development, *International Journal of Organization Behavior*, 15, pp. 457 – 468.

Poorna, D. B., Anandaraj, P. (2013). An Analysis of Stress Among the Women Mill Workers in Dindigul District of Tamil Nadu, Prabandhan: *Indian Journal of Management*, Issue: September, pp. 16 – 27.

Rahman, M. A. (2012). *Strategic Human Resource Management*, Zahin Publications, Dhaka, Bangladesh. pp. 415 – 438.

Saiyeed, D. A. (2014). Suri Nie Dhaeye Asbe (Bangla version), August 05, *The Bangladesh Pratidin*, (Editorial page, 4), Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Tasin, F. (2013). The garment sector: strength, prospects and challenges, May 21, *The Daily Star* (Business page), Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Tuten, T. L. and Neidermeyer, P.E. (2004). Performance, satisfaction and turnover in call centers: The effects of stress and optimism, *Journal of Business Research* 57, pp. 26– 34.

Van S. M., Brief, A. P. and Schuler, R. S. (1981). *Managing Job Stress*, Little Brown and Company, Boston, MA, pp: 43.

About the Author: Shaikh Moksadur Rahman is an Associate Professor in the Department of Management Studies in Comilla University, Bangladesh. His areas of expertise are Farm Management, Agricultural Marketing and Resource Management. He has published his articles in Bangladesh, Pakistan, India, Japan and USA in renowned journals. He received his Ph.D. from the Department of Resource Management and Social Sciences in Saga University, Japan having Monbusho Scholarship.